

APPLICATION OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TEAM SPORTS PREPARATION SYSTEMS

Junaydullayev Mels Asliddin ugli

Bukhara State University Department of "Sports Activities"

Associate Professor (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19555196>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 09th April 2026

Accepted: 11th April 2026

Online: 13th April 2026

KEYWORDS

In this context, it is necessary to study the differences and common features of team sports forms in the management practices of athlete preparation systems in economic science

ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of using digital technologies in managing the athlete preparation system is directly related to the nature of individual, team, and mass sports, as well as the specific features of managing the preparation system in these forms. Therefore, to accurately assess the potential for achieving high efficiency in managing individual athlete preparation systems through the use of digital educational technologies, it is essential to fully understand the differences and common aspects of management practices in both mass and team sports preparation systems.

The effectiveness of using digital technologies in managing the athlete preparation system is directly related to the nature of individual, team, and mass sports, as well as the specific features of managing the preparation system in these forms. Therefore, to accurately assess the potential for achieving high efficiency in managing individual athlete preparation systems through the use of digital educational technologies, it is essential to fully understand the differences and common aspects of management practices in both mass and team sports preparation systems.

1-picture. Types of System Management Based on Athlete Preparation Forms¹

¹ Prepared by the author

In this context, it is necessary to study the differences and common features of team sports forms in the management practices of athlete preparation systems in economic science. According to the research, when explaining the management practices of team athlete preparation systems, it is identified that high efficiency can be achieved by ensuring the mutual coordination of individual skills of athletes in the team. This is achieved through the extensive use of social-psychological, transformational leadership, and systematic approaches. These can be explained as follows:

- The social-psychological theories of managing team athlete preparation systems focus on “achieving high efficiency by ensuring proper organization of the internal psychological state of the team and their social relationships, thus enabling the normal formation of friendly relations among team members and ensuring processes such as mutual understanding and support regardless of functional distribution”.

- The essence of the transformational leadership theory in managing team athlete preparation systems is “the establishment of mutual relations between team leaders and coaches, and the implementation of personal leadership qualities to achieve strategic goals”.

- The scientific theories based on a systematic approach in managing team athlete preparation systems highlight “evaluating coaches and trainers as integral elements of a unified system, establishing the correct interrelation between them in terms of functional distribution, and achieving strategic goals through synergistic effectiveness”.

It is worth noting that the modern trends in managing team athlete preparation systems show a broad usage of theories based on a systematic approach, and the theoretical views based on social-psychological and transformational leadership approaches are displayed as integral elements of this process. This ensures an increase in the system’s flexibility and adaptability in achieving its goals. Moreover, the application of digital educational technologies in managing the system, especially in processes related to “creating interconnections between sports training loads and educational content” and “introducing automated analytical elements into system management through digital programs like LMS platforms”, highlights the scientific views in digital and innovative directions.

2-picture. The structural composition of the formation of digital education platforms in the management of team athletes' training systems.²

Our studies have shown that the use of socio-psychological, transformational leadership, and systemic approaches in the modern practices of managing the training systems of team athletes, based on digital education technologies, provides the opportunity to achieve high efficiency. In addition, it has been demonstrated that the use of technologies such as video recording and motion capture analysis, automated data analysis (Big Data + AI), athlete movement tracking (GPS and Wearable Devices), and online education and training platforms (LMS → Moodle + AR / VR) plays a crucial role in improving the coordination practices in line with strategic goals in the management of team athletes' training systems (see Table 1). The conducted studies underline the uniqueness of using digital education technologies in managing team athletes' training systems, emphasizing their ability to target multiple participants, foster interconnection and cooperation, and enhance the effectiveness of team decision-making.

Additionally, in explaining the effectiveness of using socio-psychological approaches in the management of team athletes' training systems, it is necessary to rely on the fundamental research of D. Cartz on "Social Psychology of Sports Teams". The findings of this research scientifically substantiate that the effectiveness of system management is reflected in the ability to fully utilize the competitive advantages of one sports team over another through a systematic analysis of the psychological, physical, tactical, and technical readiness of the team in the collective form of sports preparation management.

Used literature:

1. Brustad R., Ritter-Taylor M. Applying Social Psychological Perspectives to the Sport Psychology Consulting Process. *Sport Psychologist*, Vol. 11 (1), 1997. – pp. 107-119
2. Mach M., Ferreira A.I., Abrantes A.C.M. Transformational Leadership and Team Performance in Sports Teams: A Conditional Indirect Model. *Applied Psychology*. Vol. 71, Issue 2, 2022. – pp. 662-694
3. Slack T., Parent M.M. *Understanding Sport Organizations: The Application of Organization Theory*. 2nd ed. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics. 2006. – 355 pages
4. Chelladurai P. *Managing Organizations for Sport and Physical Activity: A Systems Perspective*. 4th edition. New York: Routledge. 2014. – 472 pages.
5. Katz D., Kahn R.L. *The Social Psychology of Organizations*. Wiley Eastern Private Limited, New Dehli. First Wiley Eastern Reprint 1970. – 498 pages

² Prepared by the author